

A Multi-Dimensional Visual Analytics Tool for the Security Posture of Open-Source Software

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Abstract—Open-source software is widely used by developers and businesses, but assessing its security posture is challenging due to the lack of time and specialized expertise. Existing visual security analysis tools for open-source projects primarily focus on vulnerabilities within the source code, lacking a comprehensive assessment of the project’s overall security posture. To address these issues, we propose a multi-dimensional visual analytics tool for evaluating the security posture of open-source projects. Our tool integrates data from code commits, contributor activity, and historical vulnerability duration, providing a comprehensive view of project security.

Our tool integrates data from multiple sources, including the National Vulnerability Database (NVD) and GitHub commit histories, and applies the SZZ algorithm to identify both vulnerability-fixing and inducing commits. We tested the dashboard on two popular GitHub projects, each containing thousands of commits and hundreds of vulnerabilities, allowing users to easily track development and vulnerability management within each project. An evaluation study with experienced developers confirmed the dashboard’s effectiveness in helping users quickly understand developer interactions and the project’s overall approach to security management. Our contributions include a comprehensive vulnerability dataset and a visual dashboard that offers a multi-dimensional perspective on open-source project security, meeting the needs of various stakeholders.

Index Terms—software security, security dashboard, open-source, GitHub.

I. INTRODUCTION

Both individual developers and businesses widely use open-source software as a foundation for building their applications [1]. While evaluating an open-source project’s functionality is relatively straightforward, assessing its security posture is much more challenging. Users of open-source projects often lack the time and specialized security expertise required for a thorough evaluation [3]. Open-source project managers and contributors face similar constraints, and adding a dedicated security team to every project is typically impractical [22]. Consequently, there is a strong demand for analytics tools that can effectively assess the trustworthiness of open-source projects, providing users with actionable security insights. Consequently, there is a pressing need for analytics tools that can help diverse stakeholders assess the trustworthiness and security of open-source projects.

When stakeholders seek to determine the security of an open-source project, they often turn to Static Analysis Security Testing (SAST) tools to detect vulnerabilities in the

existing code. However, these tools have limitations, including high false-positive rates and text-based reports that are time-intensive to interpret [2]. Furthermore, SAST tools focus exclusively on current code vulnerabilities, offering a limited perspective on the project’s overall security posture. Security posture encompasses a broader evaluation, taking into account the project’s development process and a more holistic view of potential risks. To address this need, we propose a multi-dimensional visual analytics tool to assess the security posture of open-source projects.

Visualization tools enable users to focus effectively on critical areas by providing an intuitive and information-rich interface. While previous studies have introduced visual tools for security analysis in open-source projects, these have been largely focused on code-level information. For example, Dening et al. [4] developed VULNEX, which audits vulnerabilities in third-party libraries within software. Similarly, Schreiber et al. [7] created a dashboard that performs static code analysis on commits during the development process. Although their work is similar to ours in its visual approach to security issues, these studies primarily examine source code vulnerabilities. Our approach, by contrast, provides a more comprehensive security posture assessment through a multi-dimensional analysis of both code and contextual project data.

Recognizing that software vulnerabilities are influenced by a range of factors beyond code quality alone, we incorporate multiple dimensions into our analysis. The first dimension is code commits: large commits and rapid sequences of bursts of big commits are often associated with vulnerabilities and defects [25], a correlation our dashboard visually represents (Fig. 1A, Fig. 1C). The second dimension is contributor data. Using color-coded markers, we identify commits that induce or fix vulnerabilities and analyze the relationship between a contributor’s activity level and code quality (Fig. 1B). The third dimension is historical vulnerability duration, which allows us to observe whether the time taken to address vulnerabilities is associated with their severity (Fig. 1D).

We selected two popular GitHub projects—Odoo [23] and ImageMagick [24]—as case studies. We compile a vulnerability dataset for each project and present these data through a dashboard. In addition to collecting project-specific vulnerabilities from the National Vulnerability Database (NVD) [15], we identify further vulnerabilities across all project commits, en-

Fig. 1. Dashboard illustration of Odoo.

riching the dataset to include both vulnerability-fixing commits and their corresponding inducing commits, as identified by the SZZ algorithm [12]. Furthermore, we collect and analyze detailed data on all commits and developer contributions within each project. These projects each contain a substantial number of commits and historical vulnerabilities: Odoo has 180,090 commits and 90 historical vulnerabilities and ImageMagick has 22,484 commits and 102 historical vulnerabilities. To evaluate the tool’s effectiveness, we conducted a user study with participants experienced in software project development, testing whether the dashboard could facilitate a rapid understanding of the security status of open-source projects. The evaluation indicates that our dashboard effectively aids users in gaining a rapid understanding of the relationships among project developers, as well as the project’s overall commitment to addressing security issues. Additionally, we have open-sourced our code and dataset for building the project dashboard, enabling users to easily access and review project details¹.

In this work, our contributions include developing a comprehensive vulnerability dataset from multiple sources and designing a visual dashboard that integrates these diverse data dimensions. This dashboard offers an in-depth view of the security posture of open-source projects, providing a clearer, multi-dimensional perspective for stakeholders.

In Section II, we provide background information, followed by an overview of related work in Section III. Section IV presents the motivation behind designing a multi-dimensional visual analytics tool and describes our data collection process. Section V offers detailed information on the tool’s implementation. In Section VI, we describe the evaluation of our tool based on user testing, and in Section VII, we discuss the results.

II. BACKGROUND

Our research utilizes data from both open-source code and development process records available on GitHub. GitHub, a widely-used platform for open-source repositories, closely mirrors real-world development environments. The platform stores various forms of development information, including source code files, commit logs, commit details, commit contributors, and issue records. To collect vulnerabilities from specific repositories, we rely on the Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) records [14]. CVE records provide detailed information about vulnerabilities, such as their severity, associated weakness types, and known affected software configurations. We automatically collect and curate a vulnerability dataset from CVE records available in the National Vulnerability Database (NVD) [15], which compiles and provides public information on known software vulnerabilities and their causes.

We collect vulnerability-fixing commits from the repository using data from the NVD. Then, we apply the SZZ

algorithm [16] to identify the corresponding Vulnerability-Contributing Commits (VCCs), also known as vulnerability-inducing commits, within the repository. The SZZ algorithm identifies VCCs by tracking changes in deleted lines within a given vulnerability-fixing commit. For each modified file, the algorithm first computes the `git-diff` between the current and previous commits to identify changed lines. Then, using `git-blame`, it pinpoints the commits that last modified deleted lines, potentially surfacing flawed code. For added lines, the algorithm also analyzes the surrounding context—up to three lines before and after—searching for any missing checks, such as `if` or `try-catch` statements. To improve relevance, empty/comment lines and non-source code files (e.g., documentation or build files) are excluded. This filtering prevents unrelated files from obscuring build-related vulnerabilities. Regular expressions further refine the analysis by omitting paths in directories like `test`, while merge commits are disregarded since they show no actual code modifications. Changes containing only new functions or methods are also filtered out, using *LIZARD* [17] to parse various programming languages and detect these cases. In instances where a vulnerability was addressed across multiple commits, the algorithm consolidated the complete set of VCCs by taking the union of all results from each fixing commit. Additionally, the `git-blame` tool automatically tracks renamed files, ensuring continuity across file history. This VCC detection process was implemented using the *PyDriller* library’s SZZ algorithm [19], with the enhancements and custom heuristics described above.

III. RELATED WORK

Visual Security Analysis Tools. In software development, ensuring the security posture of a project is crucial for developers. Visual representations of security reports can significantly improve usability by providing a more intuitive and information-rich interface, enabling users to focus efficiently on the areas of greatest concern. Dennig et al. [4] introduced VULNEX, a visual analysis tool designed to audit open-source software (OSS) vulnerabilities, focusing on the examination of problematic projects, GitHub repositories, third-party libraries, and associated vulnerabilities. The objective of VULNEX is to enhance the process of identifying and mitigating software vulnerabilities. Similarly, Assal et al. [5] presented Cesar, a visual analysis system based on a treemap representation, aimed at assisting developers in eliminating vulnerabilities from their code. Cesar’s dashboard visualizes the distribution of vulnerability categories, alongside detailed vulnerability information and corresponding source code sections. Harrison et al. [8] proposed NV, a web-based tool for visualizing vulnerabilities detected by Nessus. NV leverages treemaps and linked histograms to enable developers to explore, analyze, and manage vulnerabilities in their repositories. In a related study, Alperin et al. [6] investigated more interpretable visual encodings for decision support in vulnerability assessment, focusing on fostering developer trust in risk scoring system outputs. While their work shares similarities with ours in terms of visualizing vulnerability analysis results, our study

¹<https://svm2025.blob.core.windows.net/svm2025/SVMcode.zip>

places emphasis on visualizing the commit history of software repositories.

Schreiber et al. [7] developed a dashboard for performing static code analysis on commits during the development process. Their system visualizes warnings and affected files using an Icicle chart, displays the number of warnings generated by individual static code analysis tools through a line chart, and illustrates the distribution of GitLab events with a timeline that spans various time windows. While their study shares similarities with ours in terms of visualizing security issues during the development process, their focus, like other aforementioned works, is primarily on source code as code-level information. In contrast, our study incorporates team-level and process-level data to present a comprehensive view of the repository’s security status through multi-dimensional analysis.

Vulnerability Datasets. Nikitopoulos et al. [9] introduced CrossVul, a cross-language vulnerability dataset linked to the repositories and their CVE IDs. They also provided a supplementary dataset containing commit messages based on Git. Bhandari et al. [10] presented CVEfixes, a vulnerability dataset that compiles vulnerable code and their corresponding fixes from open-source repositories, aimed at supporting vulnerability prediction, vulnerability classification, and automated vulnerability repair. Similarly, Chen et al. [11] curated a dataset of vulnerable source code by crawling security issue websites and extracting vulnerability-fixing commits and corresponding source code. While these studies are similar to ours in that they focus on collecting vulnerability datasets to analyze project development processes, they predominantly emphasize commits and source code, neglecting the developers’ experience and interaction with the tools.

Meneely et al. [13] compiled Vulnerability-Contributing Commit (VCC) data from the Apache HTTPD web server, analyzing code churn and developer activity metrics. Their study concluded that commits involving a larger number of developers and larger commit sizes are more likely to introduce vulnerabilities. Iannone et al. [12] examined the life cycle of VCCs by applying an enhanced SZZ algorithm on fixing commits from the National Vulnerability Database (NVD), improving the algorithm’s effectiveness by blaming additional lines and applying filters. These studies focus on the impact of developer metrics, which closely aligns with our work. However, as previously noted, the outputs of these studies may not be easily understood by developers who lack advanced security knowledge or training.

IV. DESIGN

In this section, we present the motivation behind our design, grounded in the perspectives of different users. To develop an effective visualization tool for security analysis of open-source repositories, our first step is to collect a comprehensive dataset that includes vulnerability-related commits and contributor information. Following this, we introduce the core design concepts of our dashboard, detailing how it facilitates security analysis.

A. Motivation

In the context of the project development process, different stakeholders have distinct requirements for our visualization tool. We considered three perspectives—the project contributors, the project manager, and the project user—to analyze their specific needs.

Project contributors aim to efficiently navigate and understand the security posture of their open-source software repositories [3]. They seek to make informed decisions during development by gaining insights into security vulnerabilities. Their goal is to identify potential vulnerabilities, assess their impact, and prioritize code improvements. A well-designed visualization tool can help developers quickly identify critical security issues and gain a clear view of how their team’s commits relate to vulnerabilities. Project managers, on the other hand, aim to gain a comprehensive understanding of the security landscape throughout a project’s history. Visualization tools can significantly reduce the time required to read through extensive text information and manually search for key insights. By analyzing historical data, these tools can also provide valuable insights into areas where new vulnerabilities are likely to emerge. Therefore, well-designed visualizations can support project managers in making informed decisions about resource allocation, enabling them to focus efforts on higher-risk components for deeper and future-oriented testing. Project users are concerned with the security posture of an open-source project before deciding to adopt it. By reviewing the repository’s history, users can assess the project’s security responsiveness and the development team’s experience. Comprehensive data allows users to easily compare the security maturity of multiple projects and make informed decisions about which project to choose.

B. Dataset Collection

Our data collection process for open-source projects is illustrated in Figure 2. We began by using the names of selected projects to search the NVD for associated CVEs. Afterward, we filtered these CVEs to ensure they referenced specific Git commits or pull requests. To verify that the CVEs corresponded to the correct projects, we cross-referenced the root URLs of the commit and pull request links (i.e., the repository links) with the corresponding GitHub repositories. For pull requests, we extracted the linked non-merge commits and treated them as vulnerability-fixing commits. From the NVD, we obtained the CVE ID, publication date, severity level, severity score, and impact score for each vulnerability. We also collected the vulnerability-fixing commit’s hash, contributor, upload date, and the number of modified lines of code.

In addition, we directly analyzed the commits in the target project’s open-source repository. This analysis involved scanning commit messages for CVE information, specifically searching for CVE IDs formatted with four or more digits (e.g., CVE-XXXX-XXXX). The data from both methods were combined, resulting in a comprehensive and reliable list of vulnerability-fixing commits. Using this list, we applied the

Fig. 2. Overview.

TABLE I
DATASET COLUMNS AND FEATURES DESCRIPTION.

Feature Name	Description
CVE ID	Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures ID
CVSS3 Score	CVE severity score and level
Project	Name of the open-source project
File Name	File name that the vulnerability is in
CVE-Fixing Commit Hash	The Commit Hash that fixed the vulnerability
CVE-Fixing Commit Data	Date of the vulnerability-fixing commit
CVE-Fixing Commit Contributor	Contributors who submit the vulnerability-fixing commit
File Change Count in CVE-Fixing Commit	Amount of files changed in the vulnerability-fixing commit
CVE-Inducing Commit Hash	The Commit Hash that induced the vulnerability
CVE-Inducing Commit Data	Date of the vulnerability-inducing commit
CVE-Inducing Commit Contributor	Contributors who submit the vulnerability-inducing commit
File Change Count in CVE-Inducing Commit	Amount of files changed in the vulnerability-inducing commit
Vulnerability Lifetime (Days)	Number of days the vulnerability exists

SZZ algorithm to identify the corresponding vulnerability-inducing commits. Table I provides an overview of our dataset, including descriptions of columns and features related to vulnerability information. Furthermore, we gathered data on all commits and contributors to analyze each contributor’s commit count, frequency, and code quality, assessing their development experience.

C. Data Visualization

We have developed a dashboard to visualize the security posture of open-source projects. Figure 1 provides an example of this dashboard. It displays multiple charts simultaneously, with detailed text information appearing when hovering over points on the graph. We use three key visualizations from different dimensions to illustrate the project’s security status.

Commit History Column Chart. This chart (Fig. 1A) visually represents the number of commits over time, alongside the identified CVEs within the project. The X-axis shows the timeline from the project’s inception to the present, while the Y-axis represents the number of commits per day. The chart highlights when vulnerabilities occurred in the project, with a horizontal line indicating the period between the vulnerability-inducing commit and the vulnerability-fixing commit. The color of the horizontal line reflects the severity of the vulnerabilities, based on their severity score, using a color scheme consistent with the NVD. The color coding for scores is as follows: Low (0.1 - 3.9) is yellow, Medium (4.0 - 6.9) is

orange, High (7.0 - 8.9) is red, and Critical (9.0 - 10.0) is black. We designed this chart to illustrate the relationship between commit bursts and vulnerabilities introduced, viewed through the commit dimension.

Contributor Data Timeline Scatter Plot. This scatter plot (Fig. 1B) visualizes data related to contributors’ commits. Similar to the other graphs, the X-axis represents the timeline, while the Y-axis lists the contributors’ names. Only contributors with more than 25 total commits, along with those who have submitted vulnerability-fixing commits, are displayed. This ensures the chart remains clear and manageable, without being cluttered by contributors with minimal contributions. Each dot in the graph represents a commit made by the respective contributor. We use the NVD’s color scheme to highlight commits introducing vulnerabilities, while green indicates commits that fix them. This allows us to observe when each contributor introduced vulnerabilities and examine their commit frequency before and after these events, providing insight into each contributor’s code quality over time.

Vulnerability Data Pie Chart. This pie chart (Fig. 1C) presents the number of files changed per vulnerability-inducing commit and the number of files changed per vulnerability-fixing commit. This helps users identify features in vulnerability-inducing commits. For example, the probability of introducing a vulnerability is higher when a centralized commit contains a large number of files, while a commit that fixes a vulnerability sometimes only targets one or two files.

Additionally, a column chart (Fig. 1D) displays the standard deviation of days taken to fix vulnerabilities, with colors corresponding to the CVSS Severity of each vulnerability. This enables us to visually examine the duration between vulnerability-inducing commits and their corresponding fixes within the project, allowing us to assess whether the time a vulnerability remains unresolved varies with its severity level.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Data Collection

We selected two widely used GitHub repositories for analysis: Odoo [23] and ImageMagick [24]. Odoo is a suite of web-based open-source business applications, and ImageMagick is a free and open-source software suite, used for editing and manipulating digital images. These repositories, with their large codebases and active development communities, are ideal candidates for examining security challenges and response strategies in real-world open-source projects.

We utilized NVDLib [18] to efficiently search for and retrieve specific vulnerabilities and their associated details from the NVD. In addition, we employed PyDriller [19] to traverse all commits within a specified repository, saving them to JSON files for subsequent analysis. Next, we identified all commits containing vulnerability fixes by searching for specific keywords. We then combined the data extracted by Pydriller with the vulnerability data from NVDLib to generate a comprehensive file containing all CVEs for the project, enriched with details on each vulnerability’s fixing commit. We employ the SZZ algorithm [12] to identify vulnerability-contributing commits (VCCs) that introduced insecure code. This algorithm traces the origin of the code modified in a fix commit, particularly by analyzing when code now enclosed by an added if-statement was initially introduced or last altered.

Based on the aforementioned implementation method, we collected the following data: from the Odoo project, 180,090 commits and 90 historical vulnerabilities along with their corresponding vulnerability-inducing commits and from the ImageMagick project, 22,484 commits and 102 historical vulnerabilities (Figure 3), along with their respective vulnerability-inducing commits.

B. Data Visualization

Based on the collected dataset, we developed an interactive dashboard to visualize the data. For this, we utilized Plotly [20], which offers a wide variety of useful chart types, including scatter plots, line charts, and bar charts, enabling dynamic and informative visualizations. To present this dashboard as a web application, we chose the Dash framework [21], a Python-based framework specifically designed for building interactive data applications. This combination of Plotly and Dash allows for an intuitive and responsive interface, providing users with an accessible way to explore and analyze the security data.

VI. EVALUATION

A. Use Case: Odoo

We analyzed the Odoo project [23] from GitHub, collecting 180,090 commits spanning from 2006 to October 2024. Based on data from the National Vulnerability Database (NVD), commit history, and project issues, we identified 90 vulnerabilities and used the SZZ algorithm to trace the corresponding vulnerability-inducing commits. To maintain a clear and concise visualization, we focused on displaying the top 120 contributors by commit volume, representing their activity over time with a dot to indicate a broader time period, rather than individual commits, to avoid excessive clustering. When a contributor’s activity during a period includes significant commits, such as those that introduced vulnerabilities, we use this key commit as a representative marker for that timeframe. Additionally, we gathered information on modified files in both vulnerability-inducing and vulnerability-fixing commits, and calculated the duration of each vulnerability’s existence. To demonstrate the usefulness of our dashboard, we analyzed the collected data to answer the following four questions. These questions reflect the security posture of the project from different dimensions.

(Q1) In which period did vulnerabilities concentrate and emerge? And in which period were vulnerabilities predominantly fixed? As shown in Figure 1A, users observed a marked concentration of vulnerability outbreaks from 2016 to 2020. Notably, with the release of a new version in 2021, a substantial portion of these vulnerabilities was addressed, leading to a noticeable stabilization in the project’s security. Following 2022, the number of vulnerabilities declined significantly, giving users a sense that the project is becoming progressively more stable.

(Q2) Which contributor frequently submits low-quality code and during which period? Based on Figure 1B, different test users offered varying answers to this question. For example, contributors 50 made a large number of medium- to high-severity commits from 2013 to 2017, while contributors 77 frequently submitted vulnerability-inducing code in 2017. Users noted that color coding provided a clear indication of code quality, particularly when black appeared, signaling a very severe vulnerability within that commit. Additionally, several users remarked that the contributors’ code quality visibly improved over time, as they submitted far fewer low-quality commits in later periods.

(Q3) Do vulnerability-inducing commits typically involve modifications to multiple files (more than five files)? Users clearly perceive the answer to this question as “yes” based on the left side of Figure 1C. However, they often find it challenging to identify a strong correlation between the number of modified files and the likelihood of vulnerabilities. For instance, certain commits may contain a large number of non-code files, which can introduce statistical bias and obscure meaningful patterns.

(Q4) Do high-risk vulnerabilities have a shorter lifespan compared to low-risk ones? Our users generally observed that

Fig. 3. Dashboard illustration of ImageMagick.

”Critical” vulnerabilities tend to have relatively short existence times, based on Figure 1D. However, they noted that ”High” and ”Medium” severity vulnerabilities often persist for similar durations. These findings imply that in many open-source projects, critical vulnerabilities may receive faster attention, but high and medium vulnerabilities can still face delays, pointing to potential gaps in prioritization strategies.

B. User Feedback

We conducted preliminary user feedback sessions with three developers experienced in using GitHub open-source projects. One of the participants had a background in software security and was familiar with concepts such as CVE and NVD. All participants provided valuable insights in response to the questions. Users without a security background often asked for further clarification on terms like ”CVE” and ”CVSS,” with some users understanding CVE but not CVSS. This feedback highlights that our dashboard is intended for users with limited security expertise, reminding us not to assume familiarity

with certain abbreviations. Instead of relying on acronyms, we should use full terms and provide brief explanations of fundamental security concepts, such as the impact and categorization of vulnerabilities.

In addition, we received some feedback on the visual representation, particularly regarding Figure 1B. Currently, we consolidate a user’s commits within a specific time period into a single dot to prevent overcrowding of points. However, some users mentioned that this approach makes it difficult to assess the details. For instance, when two users have the same number of red dots, they cannot distinguish who submitted more low-quality code. This is because, during the same time period, whether a single commit contains vulnerable code or multiple commits do, both are represented by dots of the same size.

VII. DISCUSSION

In observing Figure 1, we notice a significant drop in the volume of commits to the Odoo project in early 2020 compared to the same period in previous years. We hypothesize

that this decline is closely related to the impact of the COVID-19 lockdowns at that time. Interestingly, this reduction is not as evident in the ImageMagick project (Fig. 3A). This difference may be attributable to the nature of the projects: Odoo, as a commercially oriented project supported by a large company, likely faced more significant disruptions, while ImageMagick, a project with a smaller base of active contributors, appeared less affected.

Furthermore, we observed that several severe, critical-risk vulnerabilities in Odoo were reported during the pandemic period in 2020 (Fig. 1A). This finding deviates from previous research [25], which typically associate a surge in code contributions with an increased likelihood of vulnerability introduction. Contrary to this expectation, we see that even as the volume of Odoo commits decreased, critical vulnerabilities were still introduced. This anomaly prompts us to consider that the pandemic-related lockdowns may have affected not only the quantity of code contributions but also potentially compromised code quality. This relationship suggests that the remote work shift, coupled with pandemic-related pressures, may have impacted developer workflows, oversight, or testing rigor, thereby affecting the reliability of contributions made during this period.

From Figure 3A, we observe that the number of commits for ImageMagick has significantly declined in the past two years, indicating a decrease in its activity. However, there has been no noticeable increase in the number of vulnerabilities. Furthermore, as shown in Figure 3B, contributors 6 and 7 are the primary committers, but it is predominantly contributor 6 who is responsible for fixing vulnerabilities.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Our contributions include the development of a multi-dimensional visual analytics tool for evaluating the security posture of open-source projects. We integrated data from code commits, contributor activity, and historical vulnerabilities, providing a comprehensive view of project security. Our tool utilizes the SZZ algorithm to identify both vulnerability-inducing and fixing commits, leveraging data from the National Vulnerability Database (NVD) and GitHub commit histories. We tested the dashboard on two popular GitHub projects, and an evaluation with experienced developers demonstrated its effectiveness in helping users quickly understand project security and developer interactions.

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